

EDİTÖRE MEKTUP

LETTER TO EDITOR

TYPE I NEUROFIBROMATOSIS AND ANESTHESIA

Ayşegül Bilge, MD¹

¹University of Karamanoğlu Mehmet Bey, Department of Anesthesiology and Reanimation, Karaman, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Type 1 Neurofibromatosis is a genetic disease that can vary in severity and affect different parts of the body, so anesthetists need to take this into account. Due to the various system involvements such as respiratory, central/peripheral nerve, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, genitourinary, and gastrointestinal systems that Type- 1 neurofibromatosis may cause, anesthesia management should be carefully planned, and complications should be anticipated.

Therefore, a detailed preoperative examination is necessary.

Keywords: *Neurofibromatosis, Spinal cord, Tumor.*

Correspondence to: Ayşegül Bilge

University of Karamanoğlu Mehmet Bey, Department of Anesthesiology and Reanimation, Karaman, Türkiye

E-mail: aysegulbilge@gmail.com

Orcid: 0000-0003-2804-9589

Received December 10, 2023, **accepted** February 25, 2024

Dear Editor,

We read your article named 'A Case of Type 1 Neurofibromatosis with Corpus Callosum Agenesis' and we think that its contribution to the literature is important (1). Neurofibromatosis is a common genetic disease with varying severity and systemic involvement, which is important for anesthesiologists to consider. The anesthetic approach for patients with neurofibromatosis type 1 varies based on the severity of systemic effects (2). In about 5% of these patients, neurofibromas can be found in the oropharynx and larynx, leading to potential difficulties with laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation (3).

Patients with a history of dysphagia, dysarthria, stridor, or voice changes may experience airway problems. If suspected, nasopharynx laryngoscopy and CT or MRI imaging are required. If there is a suspicion of a potential medical condition, it is recommended to use regional anesthesia techniques. In patients with multiple cervical neurofibromas, it is suggested to perform a neck radiographic examination to prevent spinal cord damage during tracheal intubation and to exclude the possibility of cervical vertebra dislocation. Cystic pulmonary disease and pulmonary fibrosis may occur in NF-1 patients presenting with symptoms such as cough and dyspnea. Thoracic spine curvatures are common in approximately 10% of patients, and lung function may be reduced due to scoliosis/kyphosis (4).

It may be difficult to do neuraxial anesthesia on patients with spinal cord tumors and vertebral deformities. Mediastinal tumors can also obstruct the superior vena cava. Chest X-rays, thoracic CT scans, and respiratory function tests are necessary to assess respiratory function before surgery. Hypertension is the most common cardiovascular presentation of NF. It may also affect the vascular system and myocardium (hypertrophic CMP) (5). Patients with neurofibromatosis (NF) require careful anesthetic evaluation due to the increased incidence of epilepsy and the possibility of undiagnosed central nervous system (CNS) tumors. In cases of genitourinary system involvement, retroperitoneal neurofibromas may cause ureter obstruction, hydronephrosis, or bladder outlet obstruction, and bladder catheterization may be difficult.

While various studies indicate that NF1 patients may experience heightened sensitivity to neuromuscular blocking drugs (2,6,7), a comprehensive retrospective study that incorporated neuromuscular monitoring did not observe any abnormal responses (7). However, when neuromuscular blocking drugs are used in patients with neurofibromatosis, neuromuscular conduction must be monitored.

NF-1 disease symptoms are generally mild, but anesthesia management can be complicated. It is crucial to have complete information about the disease's clinical manifestations. Therefore, a systematic approach to the preoperative evaluation of these patients can help in rational perioperative management.

REFERENCES

1. Akca HM, A Case of Type 1 Neurofibromatosis with Corpus Callosum Agenesis, IJOHSON. 2022; 2(3):112-115.
2. Hirsch NP, Murphy A, Radcliffe JJ. Neurofibromatosis: clinical presentations and anaesthetic implications. *Br J Anaesth.* 2001;86:555–64.
3. Baden E, Pierce HE, Jackson WF. Multiple neurofibromatosis with oral lesions; review of the literature and report of a case. *Oral Surg.* 1955; 8: 263-280.
4. Akbarnia BA, Gabriel KR, Beckman E, et al. Prevalence of scoliosis in neurofibromatosis. *Spine.* 1992; 17: S244-S248.
5. Tedesco MA, Di Salvo G, Natale F, et al. The heart in neurofibromatosis type 1: an echocardiographic study. *Am Heart J.* 2002 May;143(5):883–888.
6. McClellan MW, Herring J, Enquist E, et al. Von Recklinghausen's disease and phaeochromocytomas. *J Urol.* 1999; 162: 1582-1586